

Some Curvature Properties of LP-Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

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Abstract: The objective of the present paper is to study the curvature tensor of the quarter-symmetric metric connection with respect to Lorentzian Para-Sasakian manifold (briefly, LP -Sasakian manifold). It is shown that if in the manifold M^n , $\tilde{W}_2 = 0$, then the manifold M^n is locally isomorphic to $S^n(1)$, where \tilde{W}_2 is the W_2 -curvature tensor of the quarter-symmetric metric connection in a LP -Sasakian manifold. Next we study generalized projective ϕ -Recurrent LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection. After that ϕ -pseudo symmetric LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection is studied and we also discuss LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection when it satisfies the condition $\tilde{P}.\tilde{S} = 0$, where \tilde{P} denotes the projective curvature tensor with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection. Further, we also study ξ -conharmonically flat LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection. Finally, we give an example of LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection.

Key Words: Quarter-symmetric metric connection, W_2 -curvature tensor, generalized projective ϕ -recurrent manifold, ϕ -pseudo symmetric LP -Sasakian manifold, projective curvature tensor, ξ -conharmonically flat LP -Sasakian manifold.

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§1. Introduction

The idea of semi-symmetric linear connection on a differentiable manifold was introduced by Friedmann and Schouten ([1]). Further, Hayden ([3]), introduced the idea of metric connection with torsion on a Riemannian manifold. In ([16]), Yano studied some curvature conditions for semi-symmetric connections in Riemannian manifolds.

The quarter-symmetric connection generalizes the semi-symmetric connection. The semi-symmetric metric connection is important in the geometry of Riemannian manifolds having also physical application; for instance, the displacement on the earth surface following a fixed

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point is metric and semi-symmetric.

In 1975, Golab ([2]) defined and studied quarter-symmetric connection in a differentiable manifold.

A linear connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ on an n -dimensional Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) is said to be a *quarter-symmetric connection* [2] if its torsion tensor \tilde{T} defined by

$$\tilde{T}(X, Y) = \tilde{\nabla}_X Y - \tilde{\nabla}_Y X - [X, Y], \quad (1.1)$$

is of the form

$$\tilde{T}(X, Y) = \eta(Y)\phi X - \eta(X)\phi Y, \quad (1.2)$$

where η is a non-zero 1-form and ϕ is a tensor field of type $(1, 1)$. In addition, if a quarter-symmetric linear connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ satisfies the condition

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X g)(Y, Z) = 0 \quad (1.3)$$

for all $X, Y, Z \in \chi(M)$, where $\chi(M)$ is the set of all differentiable vector fields on M , then $\tilde{\nabla}$ is said to be a quarter-symmetric metric connection. In particular, if $\phi X = X$ and $\phi Y = Y$ for all $X, Y \in \chi(M)$, then the quarter-symmetric connection reduces to a semi-symmetric connection [1].

On the other hand Matsumoto ([5]) introduced the notion of LP-Sasakian manifold. Then Mihai and Rosoca([9]) introduced the same notion independently and obtained several results on this manifold. LP-Sasakian manifolds are also studied by Mihai([9]), Singh([15]) and others.

Definition 1.1 A LP-Sasakian manifold is said to be generalized projective ϕ -recurrent if its curvature tensor R satisfies the condition

$$\phi^2((\nabla_W P)(X, Y)Z) = A(W)P(X, Y)Z + B(W)[g(Y, Z)X - g(Y, Z)X], \quad (1.4)$$

where A and B are 1-forms, β is non-zero and these are defined by

$$A(W) = g(W, \rho_1), B(W) = g(W, \rho_2),$$

and where ρ_1 and ρ_2 are vector fields associated with 1-forms A and B respectively and P is the projective curvature tensor for an n -dimensional Riemannian manifold M , given by

$$P(X, Y)Z = R(X, Y)Z - \frac{1}{n-1}[S(Y, Z)X - S(X, Z)Y], \quad (1.5)$$

where R and S are the curvature tensor and Ricci tensor of the manifold.

Definition 1.2 A LP-Sasakian manifold $(M^n, \phi, \xi, \eta, g)$ ($n > 2$) is said to be ϕ -pseudosymmetric

([4]) if the curvature tensor R satisfies

$$\begin{aligned}\phi^2((\nabla_W R)(X, Y)Z) &= 2A(W)R(X, Y)Z + A(X)R(W, Y)Z \\ &+ A(Y)R(X, W)Z + A(Z)R(X, Y)W \\ &+ g(R(X, Y)Z, W)\rho\end{aligned}\quad (1.6)$$

for any vector field X, Y, Z and W , where ρ is the vector field associated to the 1-form A such that $A(X) = g(X, \rho)$. In particular, if $A = 0$ then the manifold is said to be ϕ -symmetric.

After Golab([2]), Rastogi ([13], [14]) continued the systematic study of quarter-symmetric metric connection. In 1980, Mishra and Pandey ([8]) studied quarter-symmetric metric connection in a Riemannian, Kaehlerian and Sasakian manifold. In 1982, Yano and Imai([17]) studied quarter-symmetric metric connection in Hermitian and Kaehlerian manifolds. In 1991, Mukhopadhyay et al.([10]) studied quarter-symmetric metric connection on a Riemannian manifold with an almost complex structure ϕ . However these manifolds have been studied by many geometers like K. Matsumoto ([6]), K. Matsumoto and I. Mihai ([8]), I. Mihai and R. Rosca([5]) and they obtained many results on this manifold.

In 1970, Pokhariyal and Mishra ([11]) have introduced new tensor fields, called W_2 and E -tensor fields in a Riemannian manifold and studied their properties. Again, Pokhariyal ([12]) have studied some properties of these tensor fields in a Sasakian manifolds. Recently, Matsumoto, Ianus and Mihai ([6]) have studied P -Sasakian manifolds admitting W_2 and E -tensor fields. The W_2 -curvature tensor is defined by

$$W_2(X, Y)Z = R(X, Y)Z + \frac{1}{n-1}\{g(X, Z)QY - g(Y, Z)QX\}, \quad (1.7)$$

where R and Q are the curvature tensor and Ricci operator and for all $X, Y, Z \in \chi(M)$.

The conharmonic curvature tensor of LP -Sasakian Manifold M^n is given by

$$\begin{aligned}C(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z - \frac{1}{n-2}[g(Y, Z)QX - g(X, Z)QY \\ &+ S(Y, Z)X - S(X, Z)Y],\end{aligned}\quad (1.8)$$

where R and S are the curvature tensor and Ricci tensor of the manifold.

Motivated by the above studies, in the present paper, we consider the W_2 -curvature tensor of a quarter-symmetric metric connection and study some curvature conditions. Section 2 is devoted to preliminaries. In third section, we find expression for the curvature tensor, Ricci tensor and scalar curvature of LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection and investigate relations between curvature tensor (resp. Ricci tensor) with respect to the semi-symmetric metric connection and curvature tensor (resp. Ricci tensor) with respect to Levi-Civita connection. In section four, W_2 curvature tensor with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection is studied. In this section, it is seen that if $\tilde{W}_2 = 0$ in M^n , then M^n is locally isomorphic to $S^n(1)$, where \tilde{W}_2 is curvature tensor with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$. Next we have obtained some expression of Ricci tensor when $(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z).\tilde{S})(X, Y) = 0$ in LP -Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric

metric connection. In section five deals with generalized projective ϕ -Recurrent LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection. In section six, ϕ -pseudo symmetric LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection is studied. In next section, we cultivate LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection satisfying when it satisfies the condition $\tilde{P}.\tilde{S} = 0$, where \tilde{P} denotes the projective curvature tensor with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection. Finally, We study ξ -conharmonically flat LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection.

§2. Preliminaries

A n -dimensional, ($n = 2m + 1$), differentiable manifold M^n is called Lorentzian para-Sasakian (briefly, LP-Sasakian) manifold ([5], [7]) if it admits a $(1, 1)$ -tensor field ϕ , a contravariant vector field ξ , a 1-form η and a Lorentzian metric g which satisfy

$$\eta(\xi) = -1, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\phi^2 X = X + \eta(X)\xi, \quad (2.2)$$

$$g(\phi X, \phi Y) = g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y), \quad (2.3)$$

$$g(X, \xi) = \eta(X), \quad (2.4)$$

$$\nabla_X \xi = \phi X, \quad (2.5)$$

$$(\nabla_X \phi)(Y) = g(X, Y)\xi + \eta(Y)X + 2\eta(X)\eta(Y)\xi, \quad (2.6)$$

where, ∇ denotes the covariant differentiation with respect to Lorentzian metric g . It can be easily seen that in an LP-Sasakian manifold the following relations hold:

$$\phi\xi = 0, \quad \eta(\phi X) = 0, \quad (2.7)$$

$$\text{rank}(\phi) = n - 1. \quad (2.8)$$

If we put

$$\Phi(X, Y) = g(X, \phi Y), \quad (2.9)$$

for any vector field X and Y , then the tensor field $\Phi(X, Y)$ is a symmetric $(0, 2)$ -tensor field ([5]). Also since the 1-form η is closed in an LP-Sasakian manifold, we have ([5])

$$(\nabla_X \eta)(Y) = \Phi(X, Y), \quad \Phi(X, \xi) = 0 \quad (2.10)$$

for all $X, Y \in \chi(M)$.

Also in an LP-Sasakian manifold, the following relations hold ([7]):

$$g(R(X, Y)Z, \xi) = \eta(R(X, Y)Z) = g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y), \quad (2.11)$$

$$R(\xi, X)Y = g(X, Y)\xi - \eta(Y)X, \quad (2.12)$$

$$R(X, Y)\xi = \eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y, \quad (2.13)$$

$$R(\xi, X)\xi = X + \eta(X)\xi, \quad (2.14)$$

$$S(X, \xi) = (n-1)\eta(X), \quad (2.15)$$

$$QX = (n-1)X, r = n(n-1), \quad (2.16)$$

where Q is the Ricci operator, i.e.

$$g(QX, Y) = S(X, Y) \quad (2.17)$$

and r is the scalar curvature of the connection ∇ . Also

$$S(\phi X, \phi Y) = S(X, Y) + (n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y), \quad (2.18)$$

for any vector field X, Y and Z , where R and S are the Riemannian curvature tensor and Ricci tensor of the manifold respectively.

§3. Curvature tensor of LP -Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

In this section we express $\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z$ the curvature tensor with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection in terms of $R(X, Y)Z$ the curvature tensor with respect to Riemannian connection.

Let $\tilde{\nabla}$ be the linear connection and ∇ be Riemannian connection of an almost contact metric manifold such that

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_X Y + L(X, Y), \quad (3.1)$$

where L is the tensor field of type $(1, 1)$. For $\tilde{\nabla}$ to be a quarter-symmetric metric connection in M^n , we have ([2])

$$L(X, Y) = \frac{1}{2}[\tilde{T}(X, Y) + \tilde{T}'(X, Y) + \tilde{T}'(Y, X)], \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$g(\tilde{T}'(X, Y), Z) = g(\tilde{T}(X, Y), Z). \quad (3.3)$$

From the equation (1.2) and (3.3), we get

$$\tilde{T}'(X, Y) = \eta(X)\phi Y + g(\phi X, Y)\xi. \quad (3.4)$$

Now putting the equations (1.2) and (3.4) in (3.2), we obtain

$$L(X, Y) = \eta(Y)\phi X + g(\phi X, Y)\xi. \quad (3.5)$$

So, a quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ in an LP -Sasakian manifold is given by

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_Y X + \eta(Y)\phi X + g(\phi X, Y)\xi. \quad (3.6)$$

Thus the above equation gives us the relation between quarter-symmetric metric connection and the Levi-Civita connection.

The curvature tensor \tilde{R} of M^n with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ is defined by

$$\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z = \tilde{\nabla}_X \tilde{\nabla}_Y Z - \tilde{\nabla}_Y \tilde{\nabla}_X Z - \tilde{\nabla}_{[X, Y]}Z. \quad (3.7)$$

A relation between the curvature tensor of M with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ and the Riemannian connection ∇ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z + g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y - g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X \\ &+ \eta(Z)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\} + \{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi, \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where \tilde{R} and R are the Riemannian curvature tensor with respect to $\tilde{\nabla}$ and ∇ respectively.

From the equation (3.8), we get

$$\tilde{S}(Y, Z) = S(Y, Z) + (n-1)\eta(Y)\eta(Z), \quad (3.9)$$

where \tilde{S} and S are the Ricci tensor with respect to $\tilde{\nabla}$ and ∇ respectively. This gives

$$\tilde{Q}Y = QY + (n-1)\eta(Y)\xi. \quad (3.10)$$

Contracting (3.9), we obtain,

$$\tilde{r} = r - (n-1), \quad (3.11)$$

where \tilde{r} and r are the scalar curvature tensor with respect to $\tilde{\nabla}$ and ∇ respectively. Also we have

$$\tilde{R}(X, Y)\xi = 0, \quad (3.12)$$

which gives

$$\eta(\tilde{R}(X, Y)\xi) = 0, \quad (3.13)$$

and

$$\tilde{R}(\xi, Y)Z = 0, \quad (3.14)$$

which gives

$$\eta(\tilde{R}(\xi, Y)Z) = 0. \quad (3.15)$$

§4. W_2 -Curvature Tensor of LP -Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

The W_2 -curvature tensor of LP -Sasakian manifold M^n with respect to quarter-symmetric met-

ric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ is given by

$$\tilde{W}_2(X, Y)Z = \tilde{R}(X, Y)Z + \frac{1}{n-1}\{g(X, Z)\tilde{Q}Y - g(Y, Z)\tilde{Q}X\}. \quad (4.1)$$

Using the equations (3.8) and (3.10) in (4.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{W}_2(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z + g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y - g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X \\ &+ \eta(Z)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\} \\ &+ \{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi \\ &+ \frac{1}{n-1}[g(X, Z)\{QY + (n-1)\eta(Y)\xi\} \\ &- g(Y, Z)\{QX + (n-1)\eta(X)\xi\}]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

Now using the equation (1.7) in (4.2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{W}_2(X, Y)Z &= W_2(X, Y)Z + g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y - g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X \\ &+ \eta(Z)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\} \\ &+ \{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi \\ &+ \frac{1}{n-1}[g(X, Z)(n-1)\eta(Y)\xi \\ &- g(Y, Z)(n-1)\eta(X)\xi]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Putting $Z = \xi$ in (4.3) and using the equations (2.1), (2.4), (2.7) and (1.7), we get

$$\tilde{W}_2(X, Y)\xi = \eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X, \quad (4.4)$$

which gives

$$\eta(\tilde{W}_2(X, Y)\xi) = 0. \quad (4.5)$$

Again putting $X = \xi$ in (4.3) and using the equations (2.1), (2.4), (2.7), (2.12) and (1.7), we get

$$\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Y)Z = \eta(Z)Y + \eta(Y)\eta(Z)\xi. \quad (4.6)$$

This gives

$$\eta(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Y)Z) = 0. \quad (4.7)$$

Theorem 4.1 *In LP-Sasakian Manifold M^n , if the W_2 -Curvature tensor of with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection vanishes, then it is locally isomorphic to $S^n(1)$.*

Proof Let $\tilde{W}_2 = 0$. From the equation (4.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} R(X, Y)Z &= g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X - g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y + \eta(Z)\{\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X\} \\ &+ \{g(X, Z)\eta(Y) - g(Y, Z)\eta(X)\}\xi - \frac{1}{n-1}[g(X, Z)\{QY + (n-1)\eta(Y)\xi\} \\ &- g(Y, Z)\{QX + (n-1)\eta(X)\xi\}]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

Taking the inner product of the above equation and using (2.1), (2.4), (2.7), we get

$$\eta(R(X, Y)Z) = \{g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y\}, \quad (4.9)$$

which gives

$$R(X, Y, Z, U) = \{g(Y, Z)g(X, U) - g(X, Z)g(Y, U)\}. \quad (4.10)$$

This shows that M^n is a space of constant curvature is 1, that is, it is locally isomorphic to $S^n(1)$. \square

Suppose let $(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z).\tilde{S})(X, Y) = 0$. This gives

$$\tilde{S}(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z)X, Y) + \tilde{S}(X, \tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z)Y) = 0. \quad (4.11)$$

Now using the equation (3.9) in (4.11), we get

$$\begin{aligned} S(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z)X, Y) + (n-1)\eta(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z)X)\eta(Y) \\ S(X, \tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z)Y) + (n-1)\eta(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z)Y)\eta(X) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

Using the equation (2.15), (4.6) and (4.7) in (4.12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(X)S(Y, Z) + (n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) + \eta(Y)S(X, Z) \\ + (n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

Putting $X = \xi$ and using the equation (2.1) and (2.4) in (4.13), we get

$$S(Y, Z) = (1-n)\eta(Y)\eta(Z). \quad (4.14)$$

So, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 4.2 *A LP-Sasakian manifold M^n with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ satisfying $(\tilde{W}_2(\xi, Z).\tilde{S})(X, Y) = 0$ is the product of two 1-forms.*

§5. Generalized Projective ϕ -Recurrent LP-Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

The projective curvature tensor for an n -dimensional Riemannian manifold M with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection is given by

$$\tilde{P}(X, Y)Z = \tilde{R}(X, Y)Z - \frac{1}{n-1}[\tilde{S}(Y, Z)X - \tilde{S}(X, Z)Y], \quad (5.1)$$

where R and S are the curvature tensor and Ricci tensor of the manifold.

Let us consider generalized projective ϕ -recurrent LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to

quarter-symmetric metric connection. By virtue of (1.4) and (2.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{P})(X, Y)Z &+ \eta((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{P})(X, Y)Z)\xi = A(W)\tilde{P}(X, Y)Z \\ &+ B(W)[g(Y, Z)X - g(X, Z)Y], \end{aligned} \quad (5.2)$$

from which it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} g((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{P})(X, Y)Z, U) &+ \eta((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{P})(X, Y)Z)\eta(U) = A(W)g(\tilde{P}(X, Y)Z, U) \\ &+ B(W)[g(Y, Z)g(X, U) - g(X, Z)g(Y, U)]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

Let $\{e_i\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be an orthonormal basis of the tangent space at any point of the manifold. Then putting $X = U = e_i$ in (5.3) and taking summation over i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{S})(X, U) &- \frac{\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{r}}{n-1}g(X, U) + \frac{(\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{S})(X, U)}{n-1} - (\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{S})(X, \xi)\eta(U) \\ &+ \frac{\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{r}}{n-1}\eta(X)\eta(U) - \frac{(\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{S})(X, U)}{n-1}\eta(U) \\ &= A(W)\left[\frac{n}{n-1}\tilde{S}(X, U) - \frac{\tilde{r}}{n-1}g(X, U)\right] \\ &+ 2nB(W)g(X, U). \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

Putting $U = \xi$ in (5.4) and using the equation (3.6), (3.9) and (3.11), we obtain

$$A(W)\left[1 - \frac{r}{n-1}\right]\eta(X) + (n-1)B(W)\eta(X) = 0. \quad (5.5)$$

Putting $X = \xi$ in (5.5), we get

$$B(W) = \left[\frac{r-n+1}{(n-1)^2}\right]A(W). \quad (5.6)$$

Thus we can state the following theorem.

Theorem 5.1 *In a generalized projective ϕ -current LP-Sasakian manifold M^n ($n > 2$), the 1-forms A and B are related as (5.6).*

§6. ϕ -Pseudo Symmetric LP-Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

Definition 6.1 A LP-Sasakian manifold $(M^n, \phi, \xi, \eta, g)$ ($n > 2$) is said to be ϕ -pseudosymmetric with respect to quarter symmetric metric connection if the curvature tensor \tilde{R} satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \phi^2((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{R})(X, Y)Z) &= 2A(W)\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z + A(X)\tilde{R}(W, Y)Z \\ &+ A(Y)\tilde{R}(X, W)Z + A(Z)\tilde{R}(X, Y)W + g(\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z, W)\rho \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

for any vector field X, Y, Z and W , where ρ is the vector field associated to the 1-form A such that $A(X) = g(X, \rho)$. Now using (2.2) in (6.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{R})(X, Y)Z &+ \eta((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{R})(X, Y)Z)\xi = 2A(W)\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z \\ &+ A(X)\tilde{R}(W, Y)Z + A(Y)\tilde{R}(X, W)Z \\ &+ A(Z)\tilde{R}(X, Y)W + g(\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z, W)\rho. \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

From which it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} g((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{R})(X, Y)Z, U) &+ \eta((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{R})(X, Y)Z)\eta(U) = 2A(W)g(\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z, U) \\ &+ A(X)g(\tilde{R}(W, Y)Z, U) + A(Y)g(\tilde{R}(X, W)Z, U) \\ &+ A(Z)g(\tilde{R}(X, Y)W, U) + g(\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z, W)A(U). \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

Let $\{e_i : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ be an orthonormal basis of the tangent space at any point of the manifold. Setting $X = U = e_i$ in (6.3) and taking summation over i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, and then using (2.1), (2.4) and (2.7) in (6.3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{S})(Y, Z) &+ g((\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{R})(\xi, Y)Z, \xi) = 2A(W)\tilde{S}(Y, Z) \\ &+ A(Y)\tilde{S}(W, Z) + A(Z)\tilde{S}(Y, W) \\ &+ A(\tilde{R}(W, Y)Z) + A(\tilde{R}(W, Z)Y). \end{aligned} \quad (6.4)$$

By virtue of (3.14) it follows from (6.4) that

$$\begin{aligned} (\tilde{\nabla}_W \tilde{S})(Y, Z) &= 2A(W)\tilde{S}(Y, Z) + A(Y)\tilde{S}(W, Z) + A(Z)\tilde{S}(Y, W) \\ &+ A(\tilde{R}(W, Y)Z) + A(\tilde{R}(W, Z)Y). \end{aligned} \quad (6.5)$$

So, we have the following theorem:

Theorem 6.1 *A ϕ -pseudo symmetric LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection is pseudo Ricci symmetric with respect to quarter symmetric metric non-metric connection if and only if*

$$A(\tilde{R}(W, Y)Z) + A(\tilde{R}(W, Z)Y) = 0.$$

§7. LP-Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric

Connection Satisfying $\tilde{P}.\tilde{S} = 0$.

A LP-Sasakian manifold with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection satisfying

$$(\tilde{P}(X, Y).\tilde{S})(Z, U) = 0, \quad (7.1)$$

where \tilde{S} is the Ricci tensor with respect to a quarter-symmetric metric connection. Then, we

have

$$\tilde{S}(\tilde{P}(X, Y)Z, U) + \tilde{S}(Z, \tilde{P}(X, Y)U) = 0. \quad (7.2)$$

Putting $X = \xi$ in the equation (7.2), we have

$$\tilde{S}(\tilde{P}(\xi, Y)Z, U) + \tilde{S}(Z, \tilde{P}(\xi, Y)U) = 0. \quad (7.3)$$

In view of the equation (5.1), we have

$$\tilde{P}(\xi, Y)Z = \tilde{R}(\xi, Y)Z - \frac{1}{n-1}[\tilde{S}(Y, Z)\xi - \tilde{S}(\xi, Z)Y] \quad (7.4)$$

for $X, Y, Z \in \chi(M)$.

Using equations (3.9) and (3.14) in the equation (7.4), we get

$$\tilde{P}(\xi, Y)Z = -\frac{1}{n-1}[S(Y, Z)\xi + (n-1)\eta(Y)\eta(Z)\xi]. \quad (7.5)$$

Now using the equation (7.5) and putting $U = \xi$ in the equation (7.3) and using the equations (2.2), (2.15) and (3.9) we get

$$S(Y, Z) + (n-1)\eta(Y)\eta(Z) = 0. \quad (7.6)$$

i.e.,

$$S(Y, Z) = -(n-1)\eta(Y)\eta(Z). \quad (7.7)$$

In view of above discussions we can state the following theorem:

Theorem 7.1 *A n -dimensional LP-Sasakian manifold with a quarter-symmetric metric connection satisfying $\tilde{P}.\tilde{S} = 0$ is the product of two 1-forms.*

§8. ξ -Conharmonically Flat LP-Sasakian Manifold with Respect to

Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

The conharmonic curvature tensor of LP-Sasakian manifold M^n with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}(X, Y)Z &= \tilde{R}(X, Y)Z - \frac{1}{n-2}[g(Y, Z)\tilde{Q}X - g(X, Z)\tilde{Q}Y \\ &+ \tilde{S}(Y, Z)X - \tilde{S}(X, Z)Y], \end{aligned} \quad (8.1)$$

where \tilde{R} and \tilde{S} are the curvature tensor and Ricci tensor with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection.

Using (3.8), (3.9) and (3.10) in (8.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{C}(X, Y)Z &= R(X, Y)Z + g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y - g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X \\
&+ \eta(Z)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\} \\
&+ \{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) - g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi \\
&- \frac{1}{n-1}[g(X, Z)\{QY + (n-1)\eta(Y)\xi\} \\
&- g(Y, Z)\{QX + (n-1)\eta(X)\xi\}] \\
&- \frac{1}{n-2}[g(Y, Z)\{QX + (n-1)\eta(X)\xi\} \\
&- g(X, Z)\{QY + (n-1)\eta(Y)\xi\} + S(Y, Z)X \\
&+ (n-1)\eta(Y)\eta(Z)X - S(X, Z)Y \\
&- (n-1)\eta(X)\eta(Z)Y].
\end{aligned} \tag{8.2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{C}(X, Y)Z &= C(X, Y)Z + g(\phi X, Z)\phi Y - g(\phi Y, Z)\phi X \\
&+ \eta(Z)\{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\} + \{g(Y, Z)\eta(X) \\
&- g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\}\xi - \frac{n-1}{n-2}[g(Y, Z)\eta(X)\xi \\
&- g(X, Z)\eta(Y)\xi + \eta(Y)\eta(Z)X \\
&- \eta(X)\eta(Z)Y],
\end{aligned} \tag{8.3}$$

where C is given in (1.8). Putting $Z = \xi$ in (8.3) and using (2.1), (2.4) and (2.7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{C}(X, Y)\xi &= C(X, Y)\xi - \{\eta(Y)X - \eta(X)Y\} \\
&- \frac{n-1}{n-2}[\eta(X)Y - \eta(Y)X].
\end{aligned} \tag{8.4}$$

Suppose X and Y are orthogonal to ξ , then from (8.4), we obtain

$$\tilde{C}(X, Y)\xi = C(X, Y)\xi. \tag{8.5}$$

So, by the above discussion we can state the following theorem:

Theorem 8.1 *An n -dimensional LP-Sasakian manifold is ξ -conharmonically flat with respect to the quarter-symmetric metric connection if and only if the manifold is also ξ -conharmonically flat with respect to the Levi-Civita connection provided the vector fields X and Y are orthogonal to the associated vector field ξ .*

§9. Example 3-Dimensional LP-Sasakian Manifold with Respect to Quarter-Symmetric Metric Connection

We consider a 3-dimensional manifold $M = \{(x, y, u) \in R^3\}$, where (x, y, u) are the standard

coordinates of R^3 . Let e_1, e_2, e_3 be the vector fields on M^3 given by

$$e_1 = -e^u \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad e_2 = -e^{u-x} \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \quad e_3 = -\frac{\partial}{\partial u}.$$

Clearly, $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is a set of linearly independent vectors for each point of M and hence a basis of $\chi(M)$. The Lorentzian metric g is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} g(e_1, e_2) &= g(e_2, e_3) = g(e_1, e_3) = 0, \\ g(e_1, e_1) &= 1, \quad g(e_2, e_2) = 1, \quad g(e_3, e_3) = -1. \end{aligned}$$

Let η be the 1-form defined by $\eta(Z) = g(Z, e_3)$ for any $Z \in \chi(M)$ and the (1,1) tensor field ϕ is defined by

$$\phi e_1 = -e_1, \quad \phi e_2 = -e_2, \quad \phi e_3 = 0.$$

From the linearity of ϕ and g , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(e_3) &= -1, \\ \phi^2 X &= X + \eta(X)e_3 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$g(\phi X, \phi Y) = g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y)$$

for any $X \in \chi(M)$. Then for $e_3 = \xi$, the structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) defines a Lorentzian paracontact structure on M . Let ∇ be the Levi-Civita connection with respect to the Lorentzian metric g . Then we have

$$[e_1, e_2] = -e^u e_2, \quad [e_1, e_3] = -e_1, \quad [e_2, e_3] = -e_2.$$

Koszul's formula is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} 2g(\nabla_X Y, Z) &= Xg(Y, Z) + Yg(Z, X) - Zg(X, Y) \\ &\quad - g(X, [Y, Z]) - g(Y, [X, Z]) + g(Z, [X, Y]). \end{aligned}$$

Then from above formula we can calculate followings:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{e_1} e_1 &= e_3, \quad \nabla_{e_1} e_2 = 0, \quad \nabla_{e_1} e_3 = -e_2, \\ \nabla_{e_2} e_1 &= -e^u e_2, \quad \nabla_{e_2} e_2 = -e_3 - e^u e_1, \quad \nabla_{e_2} e_3 = -e_2, \\ \nabla_{e_3} e_1 &= 0, \quad \nabla_{e_3} e_2 = 0, \quad \nabla_{e_3} e_3 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

From the above calculations, we see that the manifold under consideration satisfies $\eta(\xi) = -1$ and $\nabla_X \xi = \phi X$. Hence the structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) is a LP -Sasakian manifold.

Using (3.6), we find $\tilde{\nabla}$, the quarter-symmetric metric connection on M following:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\nabla}_{e_1} e_1 &= 0, \quad \tilde{\nabla}_{e_1} e_2 = 0, \quad \tilde{\nabla}_{e_1} e_3 = 0, \\ \tilde{\nabla}_{e_2} e_1 &= -e^u e_2, \quad \tilde{\nabla}_{e_2} e_2 = -e^u e_1, \quad \tilde{\nabla}_{e_2} e_3 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\tilde{\nabla}_{e_3} e_1 = 0, \tilde{\nabla}_{e_3} e_2 = 0, \tilde{\nabla}_{e_3} e_3 = 0.$$

Using (1.2), the torsion tensor T , with respect to quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}(e_i, e_i) &= 0, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, 3, \\ \tilde{T}(e_1, e_2) &= 0, \quad \tilde{T}(e_1, e_3) = e_3, \quad \tilde{T}(e_2, e_3) = e_2. \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_{e_1} g)(e_2, e_3) = 0, (\tilde{\nabla}_{e_2} g)(e_3, e_1) = 0, (\tilde{\nabla}_{e_3} g)(e_1, e_2) = 0.$$

Thus M is LP-Sasakian manifold with quarter-symmetric metric connection $\tilde{\nabla}$.

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